

An Outline of Events Pertaining to the Battle of Toppur A Historical Perspective

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ABSTRACT

The Battle of Toppur stands out as a significant conflict in the annals of Indian history. In 1565, a civil war emerged between Jagga Raya and Sriranga. The utilization of cannons on a significant magnitude in the region of South India took place during the course of this particular conflict. The Vijayanagara Empire, which had already been experiencing a period of decline, suffered total devastation. The majority of historians commonly attribute the precise location of the battle to Toppur, a geographical area positioned across the Cauvery River, approximately one mile distant from Grand Anicut, presently known as Thogur. This article explores the conflict between them, how it was waged, and its effects. The legacies of the Vijayanagar Empire were highlighted.

Key words : Battle, Toppur, Vijayanagar, Nayaks

Introduction

The Vijayanagar Empire is one of the most important empires in history, The Vijayanagara kingdom was founded in 1336 CE by two brothers- Harihara and Bukkaraya. which was ruled by four dynasties namely Sangama, Saluva, Thuluva and Aravidu dynasties¹. Among them, the rulers of Sangama and Thuluva dynasties were prominent during the Mediaeval period and later defeated by the Delhi Sultanate in 1566 began to decline. Bukkar I, during his reign sent his son Kumara Kampana to defeat the arch enemy the PadaividuRajyam and Madurai sultan. Kampannan established his victory over them. All these were happened in between the year CE 1352 and 1371. The Vijayanagar dominion gradually expanded over southern India. when the emperors of Vijayanagar conquered the country from the Muslim and Tamil powers they needed loyal chiefs ready to serve them in times of peace as well as in times of war. The sovereign divided the territory into what were called Nayakattinams and entrusted them with the chieftains called Nayaks. They were equality telugus or kannadins. Krishna deva raya(1509-1529), who is considered as the greatest among the emperors of Vijayanagar extended this system to the Tamil country. During the reign of emperor Achyuta raya (1529- 1542) there were about 200 Nayaks in the Vijayanagar empire².

The word Nayak is derived from the Sanskrit term Nayaka, meaning a leader, chief Or general. The Nayaks administrated Tamil Nadu as agents of the rulers of Vijayanagar³. The organization of the Nayankara system in Tamil Nadu is traced to the last of the reign of Krishna devaraya. As the Tamil power refused to accept his supremacy and to pay tribute, he sent a powerful army under the command of three generals, Vaiyappanayakka, Vijayaraghava nayaka and Venkatappa nayak to the deep south in 1520-1521. He divided the land of the Tamils into three Nayakships Gingee under Vaiyappa nayaka , Thanjavur under Vijayaraghava nayaka and Madurai under Venkatappa nayaka. The Tamil country came to be divided among these powers. The glory of the Vijayanagar empire began to decline after the battle of Talikota in 1565. Utilizing this opportunity, the nayak revolted and freed themselves from the hegemony of the vijayanagr empire. The nayaks administrate Tamilnadu with Madurai, Tanjore, and Gingee as their capital and they became independent rulers of the regions that were under their control⁴.

Causes of civil war

Undoubtedly, the occurrence of a civil war marked a terrible shift in the historical trajectory of Vijayanagar. Venkata II, a prominent figure in the Aravidu dynasty, emerged as a significant ruler of his time. Venkata had six legally recognized wives, but he never had a son. One of the ambitious but deceitful queens in his court engaged in the act of adopting an infant from a servant maid, thereafter presenting the child as her own son. The boy grew up and married the daughter of Jeggaraya, the brother of this queen⁵. But Venkata was so concerned that his "putative son" would end up succeeding him that he chose Sriranga, the son of his older brother Rama, to be his heir before Venkata passed away in 1614. Sriranga had a reputation for being unscrupulous, but Venkata believed that Sriranga would be more trustworthy than his "putative son." This event signaled the beginning of the civil war, which shook the foundations of the Empire to their very core⁶.

Gobburi Jagga Raya, brother of the previous ruler Venkata II's favourite Queen Obayamma claimed her putative son as the King and challenged succession of Sri Ranga II. Sri Ranga II and his family endured confinement within the confines of Vellore fort. However, the Vijaynagar vassals Nayakas of Tanjore and Kalahasthi most disapproved. The prominent, influential, and patriotic chieftain of Late Venkata II, Yachama Naika of Kalahasthi (Velama by caste), did not support Jaggaraya's acts⁷. This resulted in a civil conflict in the kingdom of Vijayanagara, whose capitals are now Vellore and Chandragiri. According to Dr. Barradas in Sewell's book, the massive gathering of forces on both sides is estimated to have included as many as a million soldiers, making it one of the largest conflicts in Southern India.

Battle Of Toppur

The Battle of Toppur stands as a significant conflict in the annals of Indian history. In 1616, a civil war ensued between Jagga Raya and Sriranga. Jagga obtained the endorsement of Muttu Virappa Nayaka of Madura and Krishnappa Nayaka of Gingee. Yachama, on his part, undertook a visit to Tanjore with the purpose of securing the allegiance of Raghunatha Nayaka to the cause of Rama⁸. Jagga Raya and his allies assembled their military forces in the vicinity of Trichinopoly, situated along the banks of the Kaveri River. Yachama, leading his army from Vellore, proceeded towards this location and was later joined by the soldiers

under Raghunatha's command throughout the course of their march⁹. The decisive engagement took place at toppur, village near the grand Anicut. When Yachama and Raghunatha arrived at Toppur, they found Jaggaraya eagerly waiting for them to give them warm reception. The battle seems to have commenced with an artillery duel on perceiving Jaggaraya, Raghunatha Nayak of Tanjore commanded his troops to attack him. A fierce action ensued in which Jaggaraya and many of his friends perished. The death of Jaggaraya was the signal for the flight of his allies¹⁰. The Nayak of Gingee lost his dominion. Krishnappa of Gingee concealed his dear life within his fort and did not venture to come outside. putative son was captured¹¹. The victory in the conflict was achieved by the Raghunatha Nayak faction, alongside Yachama Naidu. Rama Deva Raya, the offspring of Sriranga II, ascended to the imperial throne at the tender age of 13¹².

The consequences of the conflict

The malevolent era of the Empire persisted beyond the conclusion of the Toppur conflict. Yatiraya, the sibling of Jaggaraya, successfully established a peaceful accord with RamadevaRaya, so solidifying their relationship by the marriage of his daughter to RamadevaRaya. Consequently, Yatiraya attained a position of considerable significance. The emergence of a fervent rivalry between Yachama Nayak and Yatiraya instigated a series of events that resulted in the Empire once again descending into a state of disarray. Bijapur and Golkonda experienced significant advantages as a result of this struggle, leading them to restart their aggressive actions towards Vijayanagar. Additionally, Madurai Nayak and Gingee nayak proclaimed their own independence during this period¹³.

Following the demise of Ramadeva Raya on 1630, the succession of the throne was bestowed upon Venkata III, as per the nomination made by his predecessor. However, the nomination was subject to dispute by one of his paternal aunts. The nation had another instance of civil conflict that persisted until 1635, after the paternal uncle met his demise at the hands of the Nayak of Gingee. The Sultans of Bijapur and Golkonda persistently engaged in their own endeavors and exerted their influence in the affairs of the Empire. Venkata, compelled by a succession of attacks originating from Golkonda, made the decision to withdraw to the dense forests of Narayanavaram, ultimately meeting his demise in October of 1641¹⁴.

The reign of Venkata III was followed by the ascension of his nephew Sriranga II, who ultimately assumed the position of the final emperor. He presided over a lengthy and tumultuous reign spanning a period of thirty years, concluding in 1672¹⁵. In 1645, Sriranga II embarked on a military campaign with the objective of consolidating his power and asserting his authority over the three Nayaks of the South. Leading an army, he proceeded to march southward. Tirumalai Nayak, the ruler of Madurai, extended an invitation to the Sultan of Golkonda to launch an assault against Sriranga's military forces from the rear. The Sultan dispatched a military force under the command of Mustafa Khan with the objective of engaging in hostilities against Sriranga's army. Sriranga II expeditiously made his way back to Vellore in order to confront the Muslim invasion. Despite displaying initial prowess in combat, the individual ultimately succumbed to defeat at the hands of Mustafa Khan¹⁶. In the final moments preceding his downfall, Sriranga III issued a final plea emphasizing Hindu nationalism, urging his subjects to unite in safeguarding the interests of the State, temples, and religious practices. However, his request was disregarded. Following the military setback, the emperor sought sanctuary in the region of Mysore. He proceeded to escape to Bednur. The individual experienced death as a source of solace during the approximate year of 1672. The demise of Sriranga II marked the full eradication of the remnants of the Vijayanagar Empire from the historical records of India and Tamil Nadu¹⁷.

Conclusion

The Battle of Toppur had a greater impact on the fortunes of the Vijayanagar empire compared to the Battle of Tallikota, which took place in 1565. Following the Battle of Tallikota, it can be observed that the Vijayanagara Empire did not suffer complete destruction. The entity maintained its position and had a significant recovery. It persisted for another century. The vassals exhibited a distinct division following the Toppur fight. The Nayaks of Madhura (Madurai) and Gingee (Jinjee) developed a hostile relationship with Tanjore (Tanjavur) and Vijaynagar, resulting in deep enmity between them. Periodically, they engaged in collusion with the Sultans of Bijapur and Golconda, wisely plotting the downfall of the empire. The Vijay Nagar Empire, despite the courageous efforts of its ruler Sri Ranga III, experienced a very short-lived existence and collapsed approximately 40 years after the fight. The Vijayanagar empire ceased to exist in 1649. As a result of this, the entirety of South India fell under the jurisdiction of control of the Deccan sultans.

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